

EIGHT FACETS OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF ALEXANDER BERNARDAZZI

Opt fațete ale arhitecturii lui Alexander Bernardazzi

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Summary. The purpose of this article is to draw attention to some elements of the architectural buildings of Chisinau by the famous architect Alexander Bernardazzi, associated with the ideas of Freemasonry.

Alexander Bernardazzi is one of the most prominent representatives of the famous dynasty.

Largely thanks to Bernardazzi, Chisinau was called the “proud capital of Bessarabia.” The name of Alexander Bernardazzi is listed among the most famous builders of the so-called “Great Temple of Solomon” (such as Thomas Sandby, Sir John Soane, Samuel Pepys Cockerell and others). The Bessarabian press wrote about Bernardazzi: “He was a typical idealist who believes in the intrinsic dignity of the human person and in the triumph of the highest principles of life – love, goodness and beauty.”

It is known that in the 1820s, a multinational Masonic lodge “Ovid, 25” operated in Chisinau, so named at the suggestion of A.S. Pushkin, according to the Romanian researcher G. Bezvikonny.

It is interesting to note that in the exhibition of the Chisinau House-Museum of A.S. Pushkin presents a mysterious Masonic attribute – an octagonal column (reminiscent of some architectural elements of Bernardazzi) with images of the zodiac signs, perhaps representing a kind of calendar.

This is the first time the topic has been raised. The author of the article relies on the works of G. Bezvikonny “Pushkin in Exile”, A. Pypin, S. Melgunov and others.

Key words: Chisinau, Bernardazzi, Masonic lodge “Ovid, 25”, octahedron.

Four generations of Bernardazzi served faithfully to Her Majesty Architecture. This is one of the unique examples in world history. From the 18th to the 20th centuries, it gave St. Petersburg and Russia several generations of architects, artists, masters of applied arts, many specialists in stone and interior decoration. Bernardazzi – a dynasty of Italian-Swiss architects and artists who worked in the Russian Empire. The Bernardazzi family came from famous builders from the Italian part of Switzerland (near the city of Lugano, in the Tessin canton of Ticino, in the village of Pambio). Many come from the Tessin – - such architects as D. Trezzini; J. M. Fontana, father and son of L. and A. Rusca; father of the architect Rossi; D. Gilardi - became famous in Russia. From here came a whole galaxy of architects who worked in almost all European countries. Multifaceted talent, characteristic of the geniuses of the Renaissance, is a genetic sign of the Bernadazzi family.

The founder of the dynasty is considered to be Carlo Bernardazzi, who taught all his four sons the skills of drawing and construction, educated them at the Milan Academy and sent them to Russia for professional and career growth. The first representative of the Bernardazzi family in Russia was the stone mason Vincenzo Bernardazzi (Vincenzo Antonio;

1718, Pambio – 1761, Pambio). He arrived in St. Petersburg in 1745, was immediately appointed a specialist in stone structures at the court of Emperor Alexander the First, and worked in the team of F.-B. Rastrelli during the reconstruction of the Anichkov Palace and the construction of the Smolny Cathedral. (Annex 1).

Three years later, the younger brothers arrived - Giovanni, Giuseppe and Antonio, who began working on the construction of St. Isaac's Cathedral. Giuseppe, whom everyone in Russia began to call Joseph, shows his abilities and talent most of all. After a quarrel with the chief architect of St. Isaac's Cathedral – Auguste Montferrand, in 1822 Giuseppe (Giuseppe Marco; Italian Giuseppe Marco Bernardazzi; Joseph Karlovich Bernardazzi; 1788, Pambio, Ticino – 1840, Pyatigorsk) and Giovanni (Johann Karlovich, Ivan Karlovich; 1782, Pambio – 1842, Pyatigorsk) left St. Petersburg and became the first architects of the Caucasian resorts. Giuseppe was an architect by training, and Giovanni was a mason – an ideal creative tandem. In fact, the brothers designed and created several cities at once, including Pyatigorsk, Kislovodsk, Essentuki. So the Caucasus, similar in climate and landscape to Switzerland, became the second homeland of the Bernardazzi brothers. Emperor Nicholas the First awarded Joseph Bernardazzi the Order of St. Vladimir, 4th degree and a diamond snuffbox, and General Ermolov with a diamond ring. Ivan Bernardazzi was awarded the Order of St. Anne, 4th degree. Joseph Karlovich bought land on which the brothers built a two-story house in the traditional style of their native canton of Ticino, with a spacious veranda and a side stone staircase. In 1828, Giuseppe married Wilhelmina Conradi (1802), daughter of Fyodor Petrovich Conradi (Friedrich Otto; 1775, Grisons – 1848), a Russian doctor of Swiss origin, the first permanent chief physician at the Caucasian Mineral Waters - the founder of the Russian branch of the Swiss Conradi family. In the new house, their son Alexander was born, who also became an architect and became more famous in Russia than his father. When the boy was 9 years old, 52-year-old Joseph Karlovich died due to a serious illness. Joseph's wife Wilhelmina and his children: Alexandra (16 years old), Alexander (9 years old) and Adelaide-Katerina (4 years old) remained in the care of his brother Johann Karlovich, who did not have his own family. Two years later, at the age of sixty, Johann himself died. The Bernardazzi brothers were buried in the ancient Necropolis cemetery in the city of Pyatigorsk. The monument at the grave of the architects has been preserved to this day. According to the Caucasian governor, Prince M.S. Vorontsov, “after the death of the Bernardazzi brothers, there is no one on the Waters worthy of bearing the name of the architect...”¹.

It is hardly possible to overestimate the contribution that Italian architects made to the appearance of Russian cities. The resorts of Caucasian Mineralnye Vody, the architectural patrimony of the Bernardazzi brothers, were no exception. It is worth adding that Giuseppe Bernardazzi was also a wonderful artist; his works painted in watercolor have been preserved.

Much of what the architects created is described in the works of Pushkin and Lermontov, the memoirs of Decembrist writers, and travel notes of foreign and Russian travelers. Bernardazzi's creations are reflected in a number of paintings by Russian artists.

It is interesting to note that the Bernardazzi brothers met and communicated with Alexander Pushkin and Mikhail Lermontov during their stay in the Caucasus. On May 15, 1829, Pushkin wrote in his “Travel to Arzrum” about his acquaintance with Bernardazzi: “From Georgievsk I went to Hot Waters. Here I found a great change: Nowadays magnificent baths and houses have been built. The boulevard, lined with sticky trees, follows the declination of Mashuk. Everywhere there are clean paths, green benches, proper flower

¹ A.B. Modylevsky, *Historical Pyatigorsk*. Pyatigorsk, 2011, p. 55

beds, bridges, pavilions. The keys are trimmed and lined with stone; everywhere there is order, cleanliness, beauty...”². This, of course, is a description of the changes created according to Bernardazzi’s plan. Perhaps it was sitting on one of these green benches that A.S. talked to him. Pushkin. In his Caucasian diary on May 15, 1829, he wrote: “Of course, the Caucasian waters now present more conveniences, more improvements. – This is the natural course of things. – But I admit: I felt sorry for their former wild, free state. “I felt sorry for our steep rocky paths, bushes and unfenced abysses along which we wandered on cool Caucasian evenings. – Of course, this region has improved, but it has lost a lot of its charm... With inexplicable sadness I spent three hours on the waters; I spoke with fullness of feeling to the dear Zhe... and Zhi... (Pushkin talks about the Bernardazzi brothers: Giuseppe and Giovanni) and tried to explain to them my sad impressions. They understood me and bid me farewell in a friendly manner.”³

In 1837, Giuseppe met with Lermontov in the house of Dr. Feodor Conradi. The poet was attracted by the art gallery collected by the doctor, and it can be assumed that the poet had something to talk about with the artist Bernardazzi⁴.

Bernardazzi, Alexander Osipovich (Iosifovich) (1831–1907) – the son of Joseph Karlovich Bernardazzi became one of the most prominent representatives of the dynasty.

At the age of 12, Alexander Bernardazzi entered the Construction School of St. Petersburg. In 1850 he completed his full course and was sent to the Bessarabia region to become an architect. Six years later (for 22 years) he becomes the chief architect of Chisinau, the administrative center of Bessarabia. This period is considered the “golden age” in the architecture of the city. Bernardazzi managed to turn Chisinau into a real European city: with paved streets, cozy parks, beautiful comfortable buildings. More than 30 buildings and structures were built in the city according to Bernardazzi’s designs, in which he used techniques and details of Italian, Byzantine and Russian architecture. Among them: the building of the Kostyuzhenskaya psychiatric hospital, the building of the city Duma (1887), the Dadiani women’s gymnasium (1865), the fire tower (1860), the Greek church (1878), the Armenian church (1891) and others; participated in the improvement of the city park (now Stefan cel Mare Park). Bernardazzi’s creative talent and professionalism were highly appreciated in the Russian Empire: the St. Petersburg Society of Civil Engineers established a memorial medal named after Bernardazzi. In 1872, Emperor Alexander II awarded him the Order of St. Stanislaus, 2nd degree. Alexander Bernardazzi was elected an Honorary Citizen of the city and an Honorary Member of the Bessarabia branch of the Imperial Technical Society. Currently, all buildings by Bernardazzi in Chisinau are taken under state protection.

In 1883, Bernardazzi moved to Odessa, where he created beautiful buildings, the crown of his talent being the famous Bristol Hotel, but he continued to design for Bessarabia.

The great architect died on August 14, 1907, during his business trip in the city of Fastov near Kiev. According to his will, he was buried in Chisinau next to his mother, at the Lutheran cemetery. Unfortunately, in the early 1950s, during the construction of a cinema, the tomb of the Bernardazzi family was barbarically destroyed...

The work of his father, grandfather and great-grandfather was continued by the sons.

² A.S. Pushkin, *Chronicle of the life and work of Alexander Pushkin*. In 4 volumes. T.3. 1829-1832. Compiled by N.A. Tarkhova. M., 1999, pp. 52-53.

³ A.S. Pushkin, *Diaries. Notes*. St. Petersburg, 1995, p. 18.

⁴ E.I. Yakovkina, *Lermontov Encyclopedia*. M., 1981, p. 341.

The architect was married twice and had two sons: architect-artist Alexander Alexandrovich and architect-engineer Evgeniy Alexandrovich. Both brothers were born in Chisinau. They were educated in St. Petersburg and in the 1910s. We managed to implement many independent projects. Alexander Bernardazzi, (Alexander Alexandrovich “Bernardazzi Jr.”; 1871–1931) worked in St. Petersburg, was a student of the famous architect Leonty Benois, and together with his father he designed a number of buildings in Odessa; after the revolution he emigrated to Harbin, where he died in 1931. Evgeniy Bernardazzi (1883-1931) served as the chief architect of Chisinau until 1931; his designs for houses and monuments have repeatedly won prestigious awards. He is the author of the pedestal of the Stefan cel Mare monument and the surrounding square. (Appendix 2)

Alexander Bernardazzi was a supporter of classicism, then neoclassicism, at the same time he gravitated towards the stylization of the Italian Renaissance with Gothic elements. The architectural development of provincial Chisinau was influenced by the best examples of world architecture, the Florentine Gothic style, which is closest to the Italian Renaissance. The main buildings whose architecture influenced Bernardazzi’s work were the main cathedral of the city of Florence, Santa Maria del Fiore and the Church of St. Michael – Orsanmichele. The façade of the City Duma building contains elements of palace architecture characteristic of the construction of fortresses and castles (a jagged outline above the entrance gate, guard towers with windows, sculptures of a lion’s head). The architecture of the Greek Church (Church of St. Panteleimon) is a striking example of a creative approach to the medieval Byzantine style. In the composition of the facade, significant attention is paid to color: the alternation of shell stone in light and grayish tones is combined with the red color of the brick, looking artistically expressive. Alexander Bernardazzi was the first to see and appreciate the beauty of our natural stone, our warm, sunny shell rock. After all, such stone was used by the Florentines and Venetians in the construction of magnificent buildings, in contrast to the gray stone of the northern countries.

The peculiarity of this building is its plan, which has the shape of a cross with equal branches, arches that cover the space of the central part of the building and serve as the basis for an octagonal light drum, completed by a dome. The building is decorated with decorative columns, colored vestibules, and stained glass windows. The stone support of the elegant metal fence is crowned with bas-reliefs in the shape of lion heads. All this gives the church extraordinary beauty.

A special feature of Alexander Bernardazzi is the fact that the architectural structures of the famous architect have many interesting and even mysterious decorative elements; they are often associated with the ideas of Freemasonry. For example, on the facade of the City Duma building, rosettes are clearly visible, complex patterns hide the faces of lions, the contours of an octagon, known in Freemasonry as the Templar Star, and other Masonic symbols⁵. We see the octagonal light drum in the architecture of the Church of St. Panteleimon. And this is not surprising if we remember that Bernardazzi’s ancestors were from Italy. Namely, Italian Freemasonry patronized the development of Masonic lodges in Moldova and Muntenia in the 18th-19th centuries.

Various flower rosettes, in accordance with alchemical ideas, can generally be considered as a solar symbol, an image of the sun, which for Masons means truth, courage, justice. Rose – Symbol of Secret Knowledge, meaning the eternity of matter and love. The

⁵ A.N. Pypin, *Russian Freemasonry of the 18th and first quarter of the 19th century*. Petrograd, 1916, p. 38.

lion is “one of the most powerful and significant Masonic symbols: Lions were included in the names of the lodges. For example, in St. Petersburg there was a lodge of Alexander the Golden Lion. It was in this lodge that Sergei Lvovich Pushkin, the poet’s father, was initiated into the Freemasons. Special lions were also included in the architectural ensemble of Masonic houses. These same Masonic lions were mentioned by Pushkin, who was well aware of their Masonic significance, in “Eugene Onegin” (“Balconies, lions on the gates...”).

Number eight is a visual expression of cosmic balance, cyclical renewal, rebirth and eternal bliss. The geometric expression of this number - the octahedron is considered an intermediate figure between a square and a circle, combining stability, constancy, and integrity. The number eight was represented as a mathematical symbol for the four cardinal directions, including intermediate directions: southeast, southwest, northeast, northwest. The octagonal baptismal fonts also contained symbolism of renewal, rebirth for eternal life. The eight-sided shape seemed intermediate between the symbolism of the square (earthly existence) and the circle (sky, eternity). In temples, the dome was supported by eight columns arranged in a square, which served to designate four directions and four intermediate points and was a figurative expression of universality.

The Masons themselves sought to hide their signs from the eyes of the profane: “The light of which Freemasonry is the treasury is shed gradually, turning to allegory, useful mystery and the greatness of symbolism.” In the oath that the candidates took, they promised “not to reveal any of the secret mysteries of free masonry.” People of the 18th century knew how to read the signs and symbols that masters included in their works. Their thoughts were agitated by metaphysical questions; they returned to the immensity of the Universe.

Therefore, trying to penetrate the spirit of the culture of that time, one cannot ignore what was associated with the Freemasons.

The symbolism of Freemasonry is in one way or another connected with architecture, both in practice and in theory. The word mason itself means mason, freemason - freemason. Literally, the origins of Freemasonry were the architects and builders of Gothic cathedrals, many of whom had the skills of masons. They gathered for the construction councils of each new cathedral from different cities and countries – both experienced and beginners. These gatherings of people united by common professional interests gradually developed their own rituals and built a hierarchy. The principle of hermeticity was cultivated – for the construction of such structures, symbolizing God and his plans, access to secret knowledge was required. Their sacredness was nourished from several sources, including, in addition to the Holy Scriptures, the teachings of the East, Ancient Egypt, the ideas of ancient times, Kabbalah, the works of Hermes Trismegistus (the founder of geometry), etc. All this greatly distinguished them from traditional craft guilds. Their meetings were traditionally held in rented tavern premises, and rituals were carried out in specially constructed hidden basements and dungeons⁶.

The name of Alexander Bernardazzi is listed among the most famous builders of the so-called “Great Temple of Solomon.” According to legend, the Temple of Solomon was built by the architect from Tire Hiram Abiff in 950 BC. e. The theoretical basis of Freemasonry is the “construction” of a just society, a “temple” of the order of the universe. And in this sense, all philosophers who talk about the ideal state, starting with King Solomon himself, can serve as sources of teaching. For many 18th-century architects, Solomon’s Temple had

⁶ S.P. Melgunov, N.P. Sidorov, *Freemasonry in its past and present*. In 2 volumes. Moscow, 1914–1915, p. 144.

the status of the ideal archetype of all buildings. Even Isaac Newton (1642–1727) proposed his reconstruction of the complex planning solution for the buildings of the temple complex.

The Masons first turned to the architecture of special buildings in 1765, when the first Masonic hall was built in Marseille, France. Alas, it did not survive. The first architect of the new Masonic Hall was Thomas Sandby, who won the competition for the best design. The opening took place in 1776.

In the 1820s, the outstanding English architect Sir John Stone created a celebration hall for communication in a narrow circle at a round table and an underground secret hall for special rituals.

Part of the façade he made has survived to this day.

In 1862–1869, the architect Samuel Pepys Cockerell, a member of the Scottish Lodge, significantly expanded the original hall, but left its interior design in a strict classical style.

The United Grand Lodge of England held an international architectural competition between 1901 and 1939 for a new Masonic building in London, which was won by Henry Victor Ashley and Winton Newman. The building was called the “Masonic Peace Memorial”, “Freemasons Hall” – since 1985 it has been open to the public.

Modern Masonic architecture no longer follows literally historical canons and, as a rule, is multifunctional.

The building of the New Exchange in Odessa, created by Alexander Bernardazzi in..., is decorated according to all the rules of a Masonic house: with all the symbolic load, a classic set of premises (club halls, a large ritual hall and much more). The building of the New Exchange (1894–1899) has many Masonic and decorative elements: symbols of drafting, construction craft (compass, square, hammer), sculpture (meter, hammer, stack), fine arts (palette with brushes) and others.

Odessa was the third largest city in the Russian Empire after the capitals, a large seaport and convenient connections with the European Mediterranean, and therefore was one of the largest centers of the Masonic movement. It is known that Alexander Bernardazzi was a member of one of the Odessa lodges. Odessa had at least four lodges and many branches, but there were no special Masonic buildings. It should be noted that the “Masonic House” was created by Alexander Bernardazzi in Odessa back in 1887–1892 (destroyed in 2016). (Although, it should be noted that the “Masonic House” was created by Alexander Bernardazzi in Odessa back in 1887–1892 (destroyed in 2016).

It is worth emphasizing that Masonic lodges are non-governmental public organizations, often charitable. Only a few could afford to build their own building; even the arrangement of the Assembly Hall required expenses.

The heyday of the Masonic movement occurred in the second half of the 19th - early 20th centuries. Quite large Masonic temples were built in cities. In addition to classical premises, they housed lecture halls, libraries, cinema and concert halls, museums, commercial and office areas⁷.

Nowadays, buildings of Masonic societies are practically not built, or have an additional function.

The activities of Masonic organizations played a large role in the struggle for independence. Odessa and Chisinau can serve as a striking example here. Odessa Masonic lodges and the Chisinau International Masonic Lodge “Ovid, 25” (so named at the suggestion

⁷ Yulia Manukya, *Architecture of Freemasonry: from the Temple of Solomon to the Odessa Exchange*. Odessa, 2012, p. 17.

of A.S. Pushkin, according to the Romanian researcher Georgiy Bezikovny), took part in the struggle for Greek independence⁸. Despite the fact that to the Chisinau lodge, in connection with the entry into it of A.S. Pushkin, the attention of researchers was riveted, little is still known about her.

The Chisinau Masonic Lodge did not operate for long - from May 1821 to January 1822. The members of the lodge were representatives of different nationalities, from different countries, from the most diverse walks of life. From Moldova (Prince Michael Suzzo, former ruler of Moldavia; boyar Rafael Garlyanda, doctor of medicine; writer Ivan Brankovich; boyar Manuel Bernardo)⁹. From Greece (Michalaki Katsika, Polykasia, Penedek), Bulgaria (Archimandrite Ephraim), Switzerland (Mitterhofer, Louis-Vincent Tardan, naturalist), France (Baron Louis Charles de Chamboneau, Baron Louis Tresca, Parisian lawyer Peter Fleury, Elia de Foix), Austria (merchant Matvey Dragushevich), Russia (General Sergei Tuchkov, Major General Pavel Pushchin, member of the Odessa Masonic Lodge «Pont Euxinsky», Major Mikhail Maksimovich, Lieutenant Colonel Peter Curto, Colonel Ivan Barozzi, Major Vladimir Raevsky, doctor Fyodor Schuller and others)¹⁰.

Because of the activities of the Chisinau Masonic lodge, on August 1, 1822, Emperor Alexander the First issued a decree “On the destruction of Masonic lodges and all secret societies” in Russia¹¹.

Part of the exhibition of the House-Museum of A.S. Pushkin is dedicated to the activities of the Chisinau Masonic Lodge. Among the exhibits, a special place occupies a mysterious Masonic attribute – an octagonal column with images of zodiac signs, constellations, numbers (reminiscent of the octahedrons of Bernardazzi’s architectural structures) – perhaps representing a kind of Masonic astrological calendar.

Astrology is the most important and wisest science of antiquity, built on the mystical knowledge of the internal connection between celestial bodies and humanity. This is one of the most significant sciences of Freemasonry. In the Masonic Mysteries, astronomy is referred to as one of the seven keys leading to spiritual wisdom.

Unfortunately, nowadays it has degenerated to the level of drawing up personal horoscopes of a person and predicting favorable days for solving everyday affairs and problems. True astrology is as much higher than modern astrology as spiritual rulers (the planet and zodiac signs) are higher than a street lamp.

Freemasons believed that there was a type of life on Sirius that included the main components of human life on Earth – this included Freemasonry. Therefore, life on Sirius, the “path of Sirius” is the destiny for most people: whoever was a Freemason on Earth will remain one there. Therefore, astronomical symbols abundantly decorated Masonic lodges and were widely used in the decorative decoration of temples, in Masonic rituals and Masonic paraphernalia¹².

⁸ G. Bezviconi, Pușkin și Basarabia, in: Din trecutul nostru. № 40-45. Chișinău. 1937, p. 19.

⁹ G. Bezviconi, *Boierimea Moldovei dintre Prut și Nistru*. Vol. 1. București, 1940. Vol. II. București. 1943, p. 44.

¹⁰ G. Bezviconi, Pușkin și Basarabia, p. 62.

¹¹ N.K. Kulman, *On the history of Freemasonry in Russia*. Chisinau Lodge, St. Petersburg, 1907, p. 118.

¹² V. Sparov, *The complete history of Freemasonry in one book*. St. Petersburg, 2010, p. 430.

Alexander Bernardazzi
Monument to the Bernardazzi brothers.

If you carefully look at the signs that Freemasonry gives, even in seemingly well-known architectural objects, you can see that undoubtedly, Masonic architects left a bright mark on the “material embodiment” of the ideas of free masons.

Grateful Chisinau residents carefully preserve the memory of their famous compatriot – Alexander Bernardazzi, who embodied his soul in the music of stone.

«You, architect, saw beauty in the white stone on the slopes,
He brought the palaces of Europe to us, reducing only the height».

Applications

Appendix 1. In March 1745, Vincenzo entered into a contract “for four years of work in St. Petersburg with payment of 250 rubles annually.” At first he worked on the reconstruction of the Tsarskoye Selo Palace with the famous architect Rastrelli, then on the construction of the Anichkov Palace complex. In April 1749, Vincenzo was transferred as a senior stone master to the construction of buildings of the Resurrection (Smolny) Monastery according to Rastrelli’s design, where he worked for nine years. In 1756, he was a member of the special Commission for the restoration of the Peter and Paul Cathedral after the fire. In 1758 he returned to his native Pambio, where he died on April 5, 1761. His son, Carlo Francesco, also worked in St. Petersburg at the beginning of the 19th century, along with his sons Antonio Vincenzo and Giuseppe Raimondo (Giuseppe Jr., named after his uncle; 1816–1891). Under the leadership of the famous architect Giacomo Quarenghi, Antonio Vincenzo participated in the construction of the building of the Catherine Institute in 1804–1807. Giuseppe-Raimondo received a diploma in architecture at the age of eighteen, and at the age of nineteen he received an invitation from the Russian emperor, working in St. Petersburg (in the Winter Palace), Kronstadt, and Moscow. In March 1840, Giuseppe turned to the Russian Academy of Arts with a request for permission to complete an architectural panorama of the city in order to receive the title of artist. Nicholas the First ordered a lithograph to be made from the original he liked. At the age of 43, the architect leaves Russia and returns to his homeland, where he works hard and fruitfully. Giuseppe Jr. passed away in 1891¹³.

¹³ Isaac Bubis, *The Architects of Bernardazzi* (in the series “Memoria Chișinăului”). Chisinau, Louisville (USA), 1997, p. 25.

Church of St. Panteleimon. Kishinev.

Masonic astrological calendar

New Exchange building. Odessa.

Appendix 2. Adelaide-Katarina Iosifovna Bernardazzi had children. Her first husband was Evgeny Feliksovich Lagorio (1833?–1862), the younger brother of the famous painter Lev Feliksovich Lagorio, the best student of Aivazovsky. Now about their son, Alexander Evgenievich Lagorio, the Brockhaus and Efron dictionary reports: “A famous Russian petrographer, professor in the department of mineralogy at the Imperial University of Warsaw. He began his scientific career at Dorpat (now Yuryev) University. A grandiose steep wall hanging over the Gyaurl-Bakh gorge on Karadag, as well as an artificial garnet lagoriolite, are named after him. Their daughter, Alexandra Evgenievich Lagorio, married Riga resident Ernst Karl Rudolf Faltin, and in 1864 the couple’s union was blessed with the birth of a son, Hermann Immanuel Faltin. She had three children: Adelaide (1886, Warsaw – 1976, Paris), Alexander (10/26/1890, Warsaw – 06/1/1965, Stockholm), Maria (1893, Warsaw – 1979, Paris). Both daughters were artists of varying degrees of fame¹⁴.

Temple of Solomon.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 87.